

4th **ESP** LAC 2023

International conference

La Serena, Chile, 6–10 November

*Sharing knowledge about ecosystem services
and natural capital to build a sustainable future*

Program booklet

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Organisation

Conference Organising Committee (COC)

Co-chairs

- **Luis Inostroza**, Mendel University in Brno – Conference chair
- **Manuel Schneider**, Corporación Regional de Desarrollo Productivo Coquimbo – Conference co-chair
- **Jiri Schneider**, Mendel University in Brno – Conference co-chair

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- **Iskra Konovska**, Ecosystem Services Partnership/ Foundation for Sustainable Development
- **Terezie Kadlčková**, Mendel University in Brno
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Scientific Program Committee (SPC)

- **Luis Inostroza**, Mendel University in Brno – chair
- **Rudolf de Groot**, Ecosystem Services Partnership/ Foundation for Sustainable Development – Co-chair
- **Jiri Schneider**, Mendel University in Brno – Conference co-chair
- **Giovanni Ávila-Flores**, Autonomous University of Baja California Sur
- **Evangelia Drakou**, Harokopio University of Athens
- **Davide Geneletti**, University of Trento
- **Laura Nahuelhual**, Universidad de Los Lagos
- **Maíra Padgurschi**, AmazonFACE Program–Task 5, BPES
- **Maria Perevochtchikova**, El Colegio de Mexico
- **Albaluz Ramos-Franco**, Fundacion Universitaria Juan de Castellanos
- **Alexander Rincon**, Universidad Nacional de Colombi
- **Daniel Rozas**, Universidad Católica de Temuco
- **Ana Tureta**, Embrapa
- **Davina Vačkářová**, Global Change Research Inst. , Czech Academy of Sciences (CzechGlobe)
- **Carla-Leanne Washbourne**, UCL
- **Wieteke Willemen**, University of Twente

Organising partners

ESP

Ecosystem Services Partnership

- MENDELU
- Faculty of Regional
- Development and
- International Studies

Conference Sponsors

Keynote Speakers

Rudolf de Groot
Foundation for Sustainable Development/
Ecosystem Services Partnership
***Making nature truly count:
economic valuation of ecosystem services
is essential to build a sustainable future***

Erik Gomez-Baggethun
Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU)/
European Society Ecological Economics (ESEE)
***To ecologize economics or to economize ecology:
Challenges in nature valuation***

Barbara Galletti Vernazzani
Centro de Conservacion Cetacea/ Pacific Whale Foundation
Cetacean Ecosystem Services – Science, Practice, and Policy

Daniela Ilona Manuschevich Vizcarra
Ministerio de Medio Ambiente/ Jefa División Recursos
Naturales y Biodiversidad
***What type of knowledge do we need to generate
to see the transformations required?
Academic reflections of the doing in the state***

Robert Costanza
University College London
Misconceptions about valuation of ecosystem services

Day-by-day schedule

Day 1: Monday 6 November

Pre-conference trainings (*Universidad Católica del Norte, Larrondo 1280, Coquimbo*)

09:00 – 11:00

ARIES – Ecosystem services modelling empowered by Artificial Intelligence theoretical (*Room: Sala Conferencia Escuela de Ciencias Empresariales*)

09:00 – 11:30

Alessandra Nguyen Xuan & Emiliana Valentini – Copernicus for Ecosystem Vulnerability Assessment in Central & South America (*Room: Auditorio María Cecilia Ramirez del Departamento de Teología*)

09:00 – 13:00

Esp. Albaluz Ramos Franco – Participatory Community Monitoring of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services: The Latin American and Caribbean Context (*Room: Sala TEAL de Escuela de Ingeniería*)

09:00 – 13:00

Malte Bührs & Lars Gruenhagen – Assessment of Ecosystem Services with IMECOGIP-toolbox (*Room: Salón Auditorio de la Escuela de Ingeniería*)

16:00 – 17:00

Pre-conference registration (*Main Hall*)

Hotel Club La Serena, Av. del Mar 1000, 1710249 La Serena, Coquimbo, Chile

17:00 – 18:00

Opening ceremony (*Room: Salón Elqui III*)

Luis Inostroza, Mendel University in Brno

Welcome words by local authorities

18:00–20:00

Welcome reception & entertainment

Gardens at Hotel Club La Serena, Av. del Mar 1000, 1710249 La Serena, Coquimbo, Chile

Day 2: Tuesday 7 November

08:30 – 09:00

Registration (*Main Hall*)

09:00 – 09:05

Opening (*Room: Salón Elqui III*)

Luis Inostroza, Mendel University in Brno

09:05 – 10:30

Keynote speakers & discussion (Room: Salón Elqui III)

- **Rudolf de Groot**, Foundation for Sustainable Development/ Ecosystem Services Partnership – ***Making nature truly count: economic valuation of ecosystem services is essential to build a sustainable future***
- **Erik Gomez-Baggethun**, Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU)/ European Society Ecological Economics (ESEE) – ***To ecologize economics or to economize ecology: Challenges in nature valuation***

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee break

11:00 – 12:30

Parallel sessions

- [B2 – A review of the current state of the ecosystem services of wetlands in the Amazon region](#), D. A.Guarín Cifuentes (**only online**) (Room: online I)
- [S8a – ¿Cómo incorporar los servicios ecosistémicos en la planificación de la conservación?](#), M. J. M. Harms, et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [T4b – Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action](#), C. Canales–Cerro et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)
- [T4c – Mapeo, análisis y modelamiento de beneficios de la naturaleza \(servicios ecosistémicos y contribuciones de la naturaleza\) a nivel local: vínculos urbano–rurales](#), S. Aranguren. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [T8 – Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services](#), J. Hermes (Room: Salón Elqui III)
- [R1 – El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica](#), A. Saldaña–Espejel et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)
- [O3 – Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice Part 1](#) (Room: online I)

12:30 – 14:00

Lunch break, buffet at Brisa Restaurant (venue)

14:00 – 15:30

Parallel sessions

- [B1a – Compartiendo experiencias en la evaluación y valoración de los servicios ecosistémicos de los manglares en América Latina y el Caribe](#), G. Avila–Flores et al. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [S9b – Experiencias de monitoreo comunitario participativo de biodiversidad y servicios ecosistémicos en Latinoamérica y el Caribe](#), A. R. Franco, et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)
- [T4b – Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action](#), C. Canales–Cerro et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)

- [T6b – Valuación económica de la pérdida de servicios ambientales de ecosistemas costeros bajo un contexto de incremento del nivel del mar](#), R. A. Canul Turriza, et al. (**only online**) (Room: online II)
- [T8 – Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services](#), J. Hermes (Room: Salón Elqui III)
- [T16 – From Science to Practice: A pragmatic guide to verifying and financing positive impacts on ecosystem services](#), W. Snell et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [T18d – Towards a certification and labelling scheme based on the ecosystem services approach](#), A. Altmann (**only online**) (Room: online II)
- [R1 – El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica](#), A. Saldaña-Espejel et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)

15:30 – 16:00

Coffee break

16:00 – 18:00

Parallel sessions

- [B3a – El verdadero valor del bosque: Diálogos y reflexión desde la perspectiva sudamericana](#), M. Saravia (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [B3b – Ecosystem services of forests in the face of climate change](#), A. Robert. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [B5 – Assessment of positive impacts on sustainability](#), M. Haddouch (**only online**) (Room: online III)
- [S3a – Fast-growing forest plantations: what kind of services and disservices?](#), A. Robert (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [S7 – Tourism as an ecosystem service – Challenges and opportunities for research and practice / El turismo como servicio ecosistémico – Retos y oportunidades para investigación y practica](#), S. Kulczyk, et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)
- [S8b – Soil ecosystem services \(SES\): bringing out of invisibility and supporting decision-making](#), R. Prado (Room: online III)
- [T1 – Evaluación participativa de servicios ecosistémicos: Herramientas para desarrollar un ejercicio transdisciplinario en el contexto latinoamericano / Participatory assessment of ecosystem services: Tools for a transdisciplinary exercise in Latin America.](#), M. Torres Gómez & P. Bachmann-Vargas (Room: Salón Elqui III)
- [R1 – El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica](#), A. Saldaña-Espejel et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)

18:00 – 24:00

Field trip, Astronomical Experience – The remaining field trips will take place on Friday

Day 3: Wednesday 8 November

08:30 – 09:00

Registration (Main Hall)

09:00 – 09:05

Opening (Room: Salón Elqui III)

Manuel Schneider, Corporación Regional de Desarrollo Productivo Coquimbo - Conference

09:05 – 10:30

Keynote speakers & discussion (Room: Salón Elqui III)

- **Barbara Galletti Vernazzani**, Centro de Conservacion Cetacea and Research Associate of Pacific Whale Foundation – **Cetacean Ecosystem Services – Science, Practice, and Policy**
- **Daniela Ilona Manushevich Vizcarra**, Ministerio de Medio Ambiente/ Jefa División Recursos Naturales y Biodiversidad – **What type of knowledge do we need to generate to see the transformations required? Academic reflections of the doing in the state**

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee break

11:00 – 12:30

Parallel sessions:

- [S3b – Climate, Biodiversity and Restoration. How to articulate them in the Forest Policy?](#), C. Dirac et al. (Room: Salón Elqui III)
- [T5 – Servicios ecosistémicos FAIR para la reducción de riesgos y como eje para la gestión sostenible del terreno / FAIR ecosystem services accounting for risk reduction and ES as a basis for sustainable land management](#), C. Aznarez et al. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [T6a – Valoración plural de la biodiversidad](#), A. R. Ruiz et al. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [T14 – Integrating Nature-based solutions in spatial planning for tackling climate change and biodiversity loss in Latin American urban and peri-urban contexts](#), D. A. R. Vasquez, et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [T20 – Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America](#), F. Benra et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)
- [R2 – Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro: servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica](#), M. Perevochtchikova et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)

12:30 – 14:00

Lunch break, buffet at Brisa Restaurant (venue)

14:00 – 15:30

Parallel sessions:

- [B10b – Research on urban ecosystem services. The state of the art and challenges for future research/La investigación sobre servicios ecosistémicos urbanos. Estado del arte y desafíos al futuro](#), L. Inostroza (Room: *Salón Elqui III*)
- [S9a – Participatory approaches for sharing knowledge on ecosystem services to improve food and water securities in the face of climate change](#), A. Schuler et al. (Room: *Salón Sotaquí*)
- [T2 – Pathways of the biodiversity–water–food–health– climate nexus in Latin America](#), A. P. Turetta, et al. (Room: *Salón Sotaquí*)
- [T7b – Proyecciones y desafíos futuros de la valoración socio-económica de los servicios ecosistémicos culturales en Latinoamérica](#), L. E. Delgado, et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui I*)
- [T9a – Desafíos y visiones de los beneficios de los bosques urbanos y periurbanos en el bienestar social y salud pública](#), G. Perez–Verdin et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui II*)
- [T9b – Food security in Wet Tropical Forests: an ecosystem services approach](#), M. Canova, et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui I*)
- [O3 – Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice Part 2](#) (Room: *Salón Incahuasi*)

15:30 – 16:00

Coffee break

16:00 – 18:00

Parallel sessions

- [B10a – Climate regulation of urban environments – From models to policies](#), D. La Rosa et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui I*)
- [S6 – Making Nature Count: Applying monetary valuation data in \(financial\) decision-making contexts](#), V. van 't Hoff, et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui III*)
- [T7a – Improving data on monetary values of ecosystem services: The ESVD in a global, Latin America and Caribbean context](#), D. de Groot, et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui III*)
- [T18c – Quantification and Valuation of ecosystem services: pathway to connect research and public policies in Latin America](#), A. P. Turetta et al. (Room: *Salón Incahuasi*)
- [T20 – Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America](#), F. Benra et al. (Room: *Salón Elqui II*)
- [R2 – Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro: servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica](#), M. Perevochtchikova et al. (Room: *Salón Sotaquí*)

18:00 – 19:00

Poster session and Marketplace

Day 4: Thursday 9 November

08:30 – 09:00

Registration

09:00 – 09:05

Opening (Room: Salón Elqui III)

Jiri Schneider, Mendel University in Brno

09:05 – 10:30

Keynote speakers & discussion (Room: Salón Elqui III)

- Robert Constanza, University College London – **Misconceptions about valuation of ecosystem services**
- Panel discussion

10:30 – 11:00

Coffee break

11:00 – 12:30

Parallel sessions:

- [B8 – Operativización de los servicios ecosistémicos para la gestión de los ecosistemas de montaña](#), C. C. Caro Vera et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)
- [B10d – Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities](#), T. Gadda. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [S9c – Towards developing effective PES mechanisms suiting Indigenous peoples and local communities](#), K. K. Sangha, et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [T18a – Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design: Coproducing in the interface of science and practice](#), P. Ruggiero et al. (Room: Salón Elqui III)
- [T18e – Servicios ecosistémicos en la toma de decisiones: ¿su aplicación ha promovido cambios en la política ambiental chilena?](#), A. J. Allendes et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)

12:30 – 14:00

Lunch break, buffet at Brisa Restaurant (venue)

14:00 – 15:30

Parallel sessions

- [B1b – Mangle defender: Un juego para enfrentar las mudanzas climáticas con ayuda de los servicios ecosistémicos](#), P. A. C. Cortes et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)
- [B10d – Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities](#), T. Gadda. (Room: Salón Incahuasi)
- [S1b – Agri-environmental indicators of Brazil: Strategic intelligence for agricultural sustainability, based on the maintenance of Ecosystem Services](#), M. Simoes, et al. (Room: Salón Elqui II)
- [T15 – Social vulnerabilities and Ecosystem Services: an emerging issue](#), R. Castro-Díaz et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)
- [T18a – Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design: Coproducing in the interface of science and practice](#), P. Ruggiero et al. (Room: Salón Elqui III)

- [O1 – Young Ecosystem Services Specialists Network \(YESS–ESP\): Experiencias desde Latinoamérica y el Caribe](#), A. R. Franco et al. (Room: Salón Sotaquí)
- [O2 – Ecosystem services and human well-being in Latin America: a relationship or an assumption?/ Servicios ecosistémicos y bienestar humano en América Latina: una relación o un supuesto?](#), V. H. Marin et al. (Room: Salón Elqui I)

15:30 – 16:00

Coffee break

16:00 – 16:30

(Room: Salón Elqui III)

16:00 – 17:00

Closing ceremony (Room: Salón Elqui III)

Reflection on the conference, closing remarks and awards

Day 5: Friday 10 November

08:30 – 18:00

Field trips:

We have carefully selected four exceptional sites for the field trips, each of which is recognized for its ecological significance and rich cultural history.

The Astronomy event is scheduled for Tuesday, and the remaining field trips will take place on Friday

- National Penguin Reserve of Humboldt
- Fray Jorge National Park Excursion

Digital platform

This is a hybrid event, meaning it will take place simultaneously in-person in La Serena and online everywhere else. To make this happen we will once again rely on the digital platform Let's Get Digital which we used in the previous conferences.

All plenaries, sessions, posters and company booths will be accessible to the online attendees in real time. Plenaries and sessions will also be recorded and available on demand. The virtual event platform will be accessible to the on-site participants as well, should they wish to make use of it.

Conference app

To reduce printing and our CO2 footprint, the COC has decided to offer a conference app instead of a printed program booklet. This version of the program booklet will only be provided as a download on [the conference website](#), in case you prefer all information in one file.

To access the ESP LAC Conference app, please go to your app store, download the app 'ESP LAC Conference'. You can also download the app here or by scanning the QR code below:

After installing the app, you can:

- Access the event program and speakers list
- Create your own daily schedule that will guide you through the day
- Stay informed and receive the latest messages and news
- Connect with attendees, speakers and exhibitors (both onsite and online)

- Find more information about the organisers and sponsors
- Find more information about the venue, locations, conference dinner
- Take notes during sessions
- Rate the posters

After downloading the app, don't forget to enable push notifications to stay up-to-date on the latest happenings and important news!

Conference awards

[The poster session](#) will be held on Wednesday, 8 November, from 18:00–18:30. As a poster session participant, you will be able to vote for the best poster through the conference app. All posters will be provided with an ID to enable the voting.

The poster winner will be announced during the closing session on Thursday 9 November.

Useful tips

To make your stay as pleasant as possible, hereby some tips for your stay:

- WiFi is freely available at the venues for the conference guests.
- If you would still like to join the field trip or conference dinner, please check on Monday at the information desk if there is still availability to sign up.
- When attending the field trip, please make sure to wear comfortable shoes. Make sure to check details on [the field trip](#) page. Also, take any necessary personal medication.

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perspectives and policy
recommendations.

Ecosystem Services Partnership

The [Ecosystem Services Partnership](#) (ESP) aims to enhance communication, coordination and cooperation, and to build a strong network of individuals and organizations. ESP enhances and encourages a diversity of approaches, while reducing unnecessary duplication of effort in the conceptualization and application of ecosystem services.

ESP connects over 3000 ecosystem services scientists, policy makers and practitioners who work together in more than 40 Working Groups and a growing number of National Networks on all continents. ESP is a membership based organisation, both institutional and individual members can subscribe. The Partnership has a specified governance structure and Executive committee.

Floorplan

(also available in the mobile app)

Appendix I:

Detailed session programs

This section provides the time schedules for the workshops as far as known upon production of this booklet. Check for possible deviations or updates at the registration desk or on the conference app.

The session programs are arranged per day:

● Day 1: Tuesday, 7 November 2023

Tuesday Morning 11:00–12:30

B2 – A review of the current state of the ecosystem services of wetlands in the Amazon region

Hosts: D. Alexander, G. Cifuentes

Room: Online Room 1

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B2-1	11:10	S. Wadhwa	The current situation of the Amazonian wetlands
B2-2	11:30	D. Guarin	A review of the current state of the ecosystem services of wetlands in the Amazon region

R1– El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica

Hosts: A.S. Espejel, N. Mazzeo

Room: Salón Sotaquí

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
R1-1	11:00	M. Perevochtchikova	Qué sabemos del monitoreo participativo en México? Propuesta conceptual desde la perspectiva socioecosistémica y revisión sistemática de literatura científica.

R1-2	11:10	L. Urtado	Tipologías de participación social en el contexto del monitoreo ambiental ciudadano: análisis y reflexiones de una experiencia piloto
R1-3	11:20	J. Jujnovsky	Cómo monitorear servicios ecosistémicos de manera participativa en el Suelo de Conservación de la Ciudad de México.
R1-4	11:30	I.D. González-Mora	Monitoreo comunitario participativo: decisiones e implicaciones en la vida de una microcuenca en Oaxaca, México.
R1-5	11:40	T. M. González-Martínez	Monitoreo colaborativo de la precipitación en zonas de montaña vinculado a procesos de deterioro y servicios ecosistémicos.
R1-6	11:50	C.M. García Rodríguez	Cuidado de la casa común: Eje agua. Ciencia ciudadana como herramienta de transformación.

S8a – Cómo incorporar los servicios ecosistémicos en la planificación de la conservación?

Hosts: M.J. Martinez Harms, L. Nahuelhual

Room: Salón Elqui I

T4b – Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action.

Hosts: C. Canales-Cerro, S.M. Funk, A. Castaneda

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T4b-1	11:00	C. Canales-Cerro	Introduction
T4b-2	11:15	A.A Alfaro Flores	Evaluación de los servicios ecosistémicos generados por comunidades microbianas en la cuenca del río Elqui, Chile
T4b-3	11:30	V. Marin	El agua para beber como servicio ecosistémico en peligro en la cuenca del río Maipo (Chile)
T4b-4	11:45	X. Vergara	Integrating ecosystem services, pressures and resilience to prioritize conservation

			efforts in marine social-ecological systems
T4b-5	12:00	C. Canales-Cerro	Comparative review of Spatial Prioritizations Based on Ecosystem Services at different spatial scales, and their relationship with biodiversity conservation.
T4b-6	12:15	M. Critchley	Assessing ecosystem service vulnerability to prioritise

T4c – Mapeo, análisis y modelamiento de beneficios de la naturaleza (servicios ecosistémicos y contribuciones de la naturaleza) a nivel local: vínculos urbano-rurales

Hosts: S. Aranguren

Room: Salón Incahuasi

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T4c-1	11:00	S. Aranguren	Mapeo, análisis y modelamiento de beneficios de la naturaleza (servicios ecosistémicos y contribuciones de la naturaleza) a nivel local: vínculos urbano-rurales
T4c-2	11:20	A. Pingarroni	Patrones espaciales de la oferta de múltiples servicios ecosistémicos y la biodiversidad en una frontera agrícola tropical
T4c-3	11:35	C.Rojas	Modelo bayesiano para describir la multifuncionalidad de servicios ecosistémicos en zonas de acueductos rurales, Caso Rio Coello, Columbia
T4c-4	11:50	B. Bularz	Cartografía indígena como herramienta de protección y gestión territorial

T8 – Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services

Hosts: J. Hermes

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T8-1	11:00	J. Hermes	Session Introduction

T8-2	11:10	J. Hermes	Modelling flows of recreational ecosystem services in Germany
T8-3	11:25	J. Spangenberg	Mapping cultural, regulating and provisioning ESS and their spatial distribution in France
T8-4	11:40	C. Pozzi	The social dimension of afforestation interventions: The case study of the Metropolitan City of Rome
T8-5	11:55	C. Busch	Unveiling the Urban Tapestry: Exploring Human-Nature Interweaving in the Co-production of Cultural Ecosystem Services
T8-6	12:10	S. Kulczyk	One landscape, multiple stories. Cultural ecosystem services as perceived by local people

O3 – Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice

Hosts: A.M. Byrne, E. Quinn

Room: Online room 3

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
O3-1	11:00	Introduction
O3-2	11:10	S. Madrigal-Martínez Evaluación de servicios ecosistémicos de aprovisionamiento mediante conocimiento local.
O3-3	11:20	J.J. Von Thaden Ugalde Medio siglo de cambios en la vegetación en un paisaje periurbano neotropical: impulsores y tendencias
O3-4	11:30	A.A. Moreno Unda Transformación, gobernanza adaptativa, análisis de redes sociales, sostenibilidad, periurbano, servicios ecosistemicos
O3-5	11:40	A. Reyes Sánchez Evaluación y Gestión para la restauración de Humedales Urbanos: El Caso del Humedal El Culebrón
O3-6	11:50	P. Thapa Disentangling human wellbeing to green infrastructure at household and community levels of the megacity Bengaluru
O3-7	12:00	F. Sica Exploring geographical competition between urban ecosystems and night-

			time lights in Latin American megacities, with implications for ecologic and economic health.
O3-8	12:10	A.S. Lemus	Soluciones Basadas en la Naturaleza y Servicios Ecosistémicos Urbanos en la planificación de las ciudades amazónicas, como estrategia de adaptación climática y gestión del riesgo.
O3-8	12:20	B. da C. C. G. Pedreira	Importance of interactions relationships between impacts and ecosystem services related to anthropic activities aimed at environmental conservation
O3-9	12:30		Questions and discussion

Tuesday Afternoon 14:00–15:30

B1a - Compartiendo experiencias en la evaluación y valoración de los servicios ecosistémicos de los manglares en América Latina y el Caribe

Hosts: G. Avila-Flores

Room: Salón Incahuasi

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B1a-1	14:00	G. Avila-Flores	Palabras de bienvenida y explicación de la dinámica de la sesión.
B1a-2	14:15	G. Avila-Flores	Identificación y valoración económica preliminar de los servicios ecosistémicos de manglares en Baja California Sur, México.
B1a-3	14:30	K.G. Oñate	The value of mangrove restoration in the Colombian Caribbean: A Meta-regression of Latin American mangrove valuation for benefit transfer.
B1a-4	14:45	E. Hernández Hernández	Tendencias globales de la investigación sobre carbono azul en manglares: un análisis bibliométrico (1986–2023).
B1a-5	15:00		Mesa de Diálogo e intercambio de experiencias

R1/S9b – El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica/ Experiencias de monitoreo comunitario participativo de biodiversidad y servicios ecosistémicos en Latinoamérica y el Caribe

Hosts: A.R. Franco, G.R. Dominguez

Room: Salón Sotaquí

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
R1/S9b-1	14:00	C.A. Soberanes	Red de Monitoreo Comunitario de la CONABIO Y Protocolo PROALAS
R1/S9b-2	14:10	T. Sanchez	Programa de Aves Urbanas.
R1/S9b-3	14:20	K. Forero Gutierrez	CaMI – Campesinos y Monitoreo Inteligente..
R1/S9b-4	14:30	E. Baldiviezo Estrada	Iniciativa multiactor de servicios agroclimáticos para enfrentar el cambio climático. sustainable governance of the Baltic Sea
R1/S9b-6	14:40	C. Sazo Díaz	Zona Norte de Quilpué, unrefugio de bienestar en la ciudad.
R1/S9b-7	14:50	P.O. González Pesántez	Comparación entre el conocimiento local y rasgosfuncionales evaluados de especies leñosas nativas seleccionadas participativamente en el bosque protector Tambillo.
R1/S9b-8	15:00		Discussion and Questions

T4b– Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action.

Hosts: C. Canales–Cerro, S.M.Funk, A. Castaneda

Room: Salón Elqui II

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T4b-1	14:00	K. Gocheva	Balancing the data: towards a Whole System data architecture to reduce assessment biases for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services

T4b-4	14:15	M. Moreno-Faguett	Planificación Espacial de Acciones de Conservación para la Gestión del Riesgo Ecosistémico
T4b-5	14:30	M. Barreto Hoffmann	Impact of invasive alien species on the ecosystem services on the archipelago of Fernando de Noronha, Brazil

T6b/T18d– Valuación económica de la pérdida de servicios ambientales de ecosistemas costeros bajo un contexto de incremento del nivel del mar/ Towards a certification and labelling scheme based on the ecosystem services approach

Hosts: A. Altmann, R.A. Canul Turriza, V.F. Díaz, A.K. Castilla, M.C.C. Lagler

Room: Online Room 1

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T6b/T18d-1	14:00	A. Altmann	Introduction
T6b/T18d-2	14:20	C. Marina	La minería de basalto en el bioma del bosque atlántico en el estado de rio grande do sul y la propuesta de certificación de ecosistema
T6b/T18d-3	14:50	R.F. de Mattos	Por una estrategia de armonización de los programas de certificación y etiquetado de los Estados Partes para fomentar modelos de producción agroecológica en el MERCOSUR basado en el concepto de servicios ecosistémicos.
T6b/T18d-4	15:20		Questions

T8– Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services

Hosts: J. Hermes

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T8-1	14:00	L. Bachi	Governance systems to promote synergies between Cultural Ecosystem Services: experiences from Germany and Brazil

T8-2	14:15	C. Hidalgo Sheers	Servicios ecosistémicos culturales recreativos en un territorio industrializado: acceso y limitantes de acceso percibidas por habitantes de zonas urbanas
T8-3	14:30	M. Bermudez-Urdaneta	Inventarios de patrimonio natural para la comprensión de servicios ecosistémicos culturales en el ordenamiento territorial: el enfoque de patrimonios integrados en Bogotá (Colombia)
T8-4	14:45	S. Uribe	Cultural Ecosystem Services and Tourism: The Coffee Cultural Landscape of Colombia
T8-5	15:00	J. Hermes	Wrap-up and discussion

T16 – From Science to Practice: A pragmatic guide to verifying and financing positive impacts on ecosystem services

Hosts: W. Snell, M.A. Lizcano Solano

Hosts: Salón Elqui I

Tuesday Afternoon 16:00–18:00

B3a – El verdadero valor del bosque: Diálogos y reflexión desde la perspectiva sudamericana

Hosts: M. Saravia

Room: Salón Incahuasi

B3b/S3a- Ecosystem services of forests in the face of climate change/ Fast-growing forest plantations: what kind of services and disservices?

Hosts: A. Robert

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B3b/S3a-1	16:00	A. Robert	Introduction
B3b/S3a-2	16:05	T. Fuentes-Castillo	Estimating Forest carbon stocks from field, satellite and drone observations:

			Monitoring of Conservation Easements in the Chilean Patagonia
B3b/S3a-3	16:20	I.L. Ochoa	Forest Fires in Chile: Assessing the Economic and Environmental Impact on the Natural Capital
B3b/S3a-4	16:35	C.B. Barriga Bahamonde	Servicio ecosistémicos mediados por mamíferos frugívoros en la Amazonía Peruana
B3b/S3a-5	16:50	L. Tourinho	Climate change impacts over ecosystem services provided by Brazilian mammals
B3b/S3a-6	17:05	C.J. Galarza	Verifying the positive impact on ecosystem services in the framework of FSC certification, as an instrument to combat climate change and biodiversity loss and to counteract the inequity that affects forest managers given the existing economic incentives that drive activities that lead to deforestation and forest degradation
B3b/S3a-7	17:20	A. Robert	Debate: How to adapt forests to climate change? What kind of forests for tomorrow?
B3b/S3a-8	17:30	A. Robert	In the face of climate change, fast-growing forest plantations encouraged because of their ecosystem services
B3b/S3a-9	17:40	A. Robert	Ecosystem services provided by poplar plantations, from the point of view of local stakeholders and inhabitants
B3b/S3a-10	17:50	A. Robert	Discussion and conclusion

R1– El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios ecosistémicos: balance de experiencias en Latinoamérica

Hosts: A.S. Espejel, L.O. Almeida Lenero, M. Perevochtchikova, N. Mazzeo

Room: Salón Sotaquí

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
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R1-1	16:00	A.Saldaña- Espejel	Aportes clave del monitoreo colaborativo para la gobernanza de los bienes comunes desde la resiliencia.
R1-2	16:10	P. Wallem	Red de Observatorios Socio-ecológicos Andinos (ROSA).
R1-4	16:20	L. Almeida Leñero	Monitoreo participativo socio ecosistémico en la Ciudad de México: experiencias, aprendizajes y recomendaciones.
R1-5	16:30	I. Gadino	Mirador Región Este: difusión del conocimiento para la participación territorial-ambiental
R1-6	16:40	O.L. Hernández-Manrique	Del dicho al hecho en la Coproducción: Modos y medios de vida en cercanías a la represa Arroyo Grande, San José de Playón, María La Baja, Bolívar, Colombia
R1-7	16:50	M. Delpino Chamy	Plataforma participativa digital para la evaluación comunitaria y técnica de servicios ecosistémicos culturales.
R1-9	17:10	All the speakers and the audience	Discussion

S7– Tourism as an ecosystem service – Challenges and opportunities for research and practice / El turismo como servicio ecosistémico – Retos y oportunidades para investigación y practica

Hosts: S. Kulczyk, S. Uribe

Room: Salón Elqui II

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
S7-1	16:00		Session Introduction
S7-2	16:05	A. Valenzuela R.	Política indígena y negocios étnicos para el turismo. Los casos del Valle de la Luna, Toconao y Socaire en San Pedro de Atacama, Chile.
S7-3	16:15	S. Uribe	Cultural Ecosystem Services and Cultural Landscape: A Colombian Coffee World Heritage Site
S7-4	16:25	R. Coupal	Small-scale Guatemalan Farmer Livelihood Risk Assessment from Climate Change in High Tourism Areas: Living

			Wage Estimates, Export Cropping, and costs of international migration
S7-5	16:35	R. WIJETHUNGA	Tourism as an ecosystem service – Challenges and opportunities for research and practice
S7-6	16:45		Discussion and Conclusion
S7-7	17:00	D. Sikorska	Exploring the Relationship between Perceived Naturalness, Biodiversity, and the Selection of Natural Areas for Cultural Ecosystem Services Delivery in Urban Environments: A Case Study in Warsaw
S7-8	17:10	M. Sylla	One day nature-based tourism in the peri-urban area – biophysical and monetary assessment
S7-9	17:20	M. Derek	Fish & Tourism? Synergies and trade-offs between cultural and provisioning ecosystem services in Mazury (Poland)
S7-10	17:30	V. Naruševičius	Challenges of Ecosystem Services Assessment and Balance in Small Islands of Inland Waters
S7-11	17:40		Discussion and Conclusion

S8b – Soil ecosystem services (SES): bringing out of invisibility and supporting decision-making

Hosts: R. Prado, E. Fidalgo

Room: Online room 1

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
S8b-1	16:00	R. Bardy Prado	Introduction
S8b-2	16:15	A. P Guarderas	Land use change alters soil-associated ecosystem services in a tropical mountain landscape of Northern Ecuador
S8b-3	16:30	J.P Fuentes-Espoz	Conocimiento local de la calidad del suelo y su asociación con servicios ecosistémicos clave por agricultores de la zona altoandina de la cuenca del Huasco, Chile

S8b-4	16:45	J.R Massenberg	From Investigation to Exploration: Unraveling Preference and Motivational Heterogeneity for Soil-Based Ecosystem Services
S8b-5	17:00	M.P Barral	SOILGUARD project: Sustainable soil management to unleash soil biodiversity potential and increase environmental, economic and social well being
S8b-6	17:15	R.M de Macedo Borges	Analysis of soil ecosystem services and their economic valuation: remediation with residual contamination in urban environments
S8b-7	17:30	F. Ungaro	Soil ecosystem services assessment and mapping in Emilia-Romagna (NE Italy): example at different scales, from the field survey to the decisionmakers' agenda
S8b-8	17:45	E. Cardoso Fidalgo	Conclusions

T1- Evaluación participativa de servicios ecosistémicos: Herramientas para desarrollar un ejercicio transdisciplinario en el contexto latinoamericano / Participatory assessment of ecosystem services: Tools for a transdisciplinary exercise in Latin America

Hosts: M.T. Gomez, P. Bachmann-Vargas

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T1-1	16:00	M. Torres. Gomez	Introduction
T1-2	16:15	A. Altamirano	Ecosystem services: human well-being importance
T1-3	16:19	A. Vallet	Knowledge coproduction to improve assessment of biodiversity and its contributions to human quality of life
T1-4	16:23	J. Monteiro	Agricultural Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) for water and food security in the context of climate change
T1-5	16:27	L.M Ramirez	Experiencias de valoración participativa de servicios ecosistémicos en el marco del licenciamiento ambiental en Colombia

T1-6	16:31	V. Roldan	Dispositivo para identificar Contribuciones de la Naturaleza a las Personas y realizar una evaluación integral
T1-7	16:35	J. Moreno	Valoración Social; Conocimiento Espacial; Justicia Ambiental; Mapeos Participativos; Conservación
T1-8	16:39	F. de la Barrera	Valoración de servicios ecosistémicos locales en amplio gradiente latitudinal: coincidencias y discrepancias de la aplicación de metodologías basadas en expertos, mediciones y consulta social
T1-9	16:45	M.T. Gomez, P. Bachmann-Vargas	Discussion and Conclusion

● Day 2: Wednesday, 8 November 2023

Wednesday Morning 11:00-12:30

R2 – Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro: servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica

Hosts: M. Perevochtchikova, C.I. Villegas Palacio, J.M. Galeana Pizaña

Room: Salón Sotaquí

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
R2-1	11:00	M. Perevochtchikova	Trayectorias socioecológicas. Revisión sistemática de literatura científica
R2-1	11:10	F. Gómez-Santiz	Medios de vida sustentables y sus implicaciones en el estado del Sistema Socio-Ecológico en 4 microcuencas del SC-CDMX: propuesta de un modelo conceptual basado en Sistemas Dinámicos
R2-3	11:20	M. Galeana Pizaña	Abordando la deforestación en áreas periurbanas: Trayectorias socioecológicas y el impacto de los instrumentos de

			política ambiental en el Suelo de Conservación de la Ciudad de México
R2-4	11:30	A. Pedraza Gama	Análisis de la vulnerabilidad socio-ecológica en cuatro microcuencas del Suelo de Conservación en la Ciudad de México
R2-5	11:40	A. Ramírez-Leon	Trayectoria histórica de un sistema socioecológico agroalimentario y los retos para su sustentabilidad
R2-6	11:50	D. P. Mejía Durango	Gobernanza, prácticas de producción agrícola y las contribuciones de la naturaleza a las personas en sistemas socio-ecológicos cafeteros
R2-7	12:00		Questions and Discussion

S3b – Climate, Biodiversity and Restoration: How to articulate them in the Forest Policy?

Hosts: C. Dirac, G. Soto

Room: Salón Elqui III

T5/T6a –FAIR ecosystem services accounting for risk reduction and ES as a basis for sustainable land management/ Valoración plura de la biodiversidad

Hosts: C. Aznarez, I. Ruiz, A. Sperotto, A.M. Torres

Room: Salón Incahuasi

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T5/T6a-1	11:00	Session hosts	Introduction
T5/T6a-2	11:10	L. Zhen	Development of the Indicator System for Evaluating Rural Ecosystem Restoration Programs in the Loess Plateau of China.
T5/T6a-3	11:20	J. A. García García	Análisis multicriterio para operacionalizar las transiciones de sostenibilidad de los sistemas agroalimentarios en el nexo agua-energía-alimentos-biodiversidad
T5/T6a-4	11:30	M. Guerrero-Gatic	Descubriendo valores plurales para avanzar en la comprensión de la relación entre valoración y gestión: el caso del desierto de Atacama.

T5/T6a-5	11:40	R.R. Puentes	El enfoque biocultural como aproximación para la valoración plural de las relaciones sociedad-naturaleza. Caso de estudio en el Guavio (Colombia).
T5/T6a-6	11:50	J.A. Garcia Garcia	Evaluación de multifuncionalidad como indicador de sostenibilidad del paisaje. Caso microcuencas
T5/T6a-7	12:00	J. Sepúlveda Garay	Visibilizando los servicios ecosistémicos desde la significación y el cuidado de semillas por mujeres en la Cuenca del Huasco, Atacama, Chile.
T5/T6a-8	12:10	M.L. Moreno	Valoración económica de la protección de servicios eco sistémicos en una zona de amortiguamiento en Costa Rica.

T14 – Integrating Nature-based solutions in spatial planning for tackling climate change and biodiversity loss in Latin American urban and peri-urban contexts

Hosts: D.A. Rozas Vasquez, J.K. Kato Huerta, M.S. Orta Ortiz

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T14-1	11:00	M. Mirsafa	Mapping Urban NBS Practices across Latin America for Climate Change Adaptation
T14-2	11:10	J. Hack	Advances in the application of Nature-based Solutions for urban water management in Latin America
T14-3	11:20	P. Bonacic	Corredor verde en Puerto Varas, Chile. Conectando la infraestructura verde y azul a la planificación urbana.
T14-4	11:30	A. Cieszewska	Will serious games convince residents to take action to adapt to climate change?
T14-5	11:40	J. Kato Huerta	Enhancing Transdisciplinary Knowledge Co-production for Effective Uptake of ES-Evidence: Insights from the SELINA Project
T14-6	11:50	M.S. Orta Ortiz	Analyzing the transformative potential of spatial planning to implement urban nature-based solutions for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem service provision

T14-7	12:00	All speakers	Discussion
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T20 – Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America

Hosts: F. Benra, L. Nahuelhual

Room: Salón Elqui II

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T20-1	11:00	J. Kato-Huerta	Inclusion of Environmental Justice concerns in Urban Climate Action Plans: Insights from Latin American Cities
T20-2	11:15	G. Benati	Spatial analysis of cultural ecosystem services and socio-economic characteristics in Cali, Colombia: enhancing equity in urban green spaces
T20-4	11:30	M. Montero-Hidalgo	Aportaciones al campo de la justicia ambiental para la gestión de los servicios de los ecosistemas.
T20-5	11:45	F. Benra	Ecosystem services supply and (in)equality archetypes
T20-6	12:00	E. Lopez-Morales	Exploring ecological gentrification by ecosystem services in Chile: a critical literature review

Wednesday Afternoon 14:00-15:30

B10b – Research on urban ecosystem services. The state of the art and challenges for future research/ La investigación sobre servicios ecosistémicos urbanos. Estado del arte y desafíos al futuro

Hosts: L. Inostroza

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B10b-1	14:00	L. Inostroza	Introduction to the session
B10b-2	14:10	M. Bührs	Potential of citizen science data driven species distribution models for habitat quality assessment in metropolitan
B10b-3	14:25	L. Gruenhagen	Which toolset (InVEST/IMECOGIP Toolbox/i-Tree Eco) to use? – A

			comparative method assessment of carbon storage in urban street trees as an ecosystem service
B10b-4	14:40	F. De la Barrera	Valoración de servicios ecosistémicos locales en amplio gradiente latitudinal: coincidencias y discrepancias de la aplicación de metodologías basadas en expertos, mediciones y consulta social
B10b-5	14:55	U. Cardenas	An Integrated Framework for Understanding the Contribution of Ecosystem Services to Urban Metabolism Assessments. Case Studies in London and Lima
B10b-6	15:10	M. Derek	This is my magical place here". Walking interviews as a method to understand CES trade-offs in urban green spaces
B10b-7	15:25	L. Inostroza	Discussion

O3– Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice

Hosts: A. Byrne, E.Quinn

Room: Salón Incahuasi

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
O3-10	14:00		Introduction
O3-11	14:05	D.P. Tyszevska	Ecosystem services in urban spaces well adapted to climate change Malmö (Sweden) case study
O3-12	14:15	N. Nagabhatla	Circular Economy for Water and Wastewater Management: Synopsis of Integration Pathways in the Latin American Region
O3-13	14:25	F. Rojas	PERCEPCIONES SOBRE SERVICIOS ECOSISTÉMICOS Y SUS FORZANTES EN EL CAMPO DUNAR DE GOTA DE LECHE, EL TABO, CHILE CENTRAL
O3-14	14:35	C. Ramírez Cabrera	Análisis de la intensidad de los cambios en las coberturas y usos del suelo y su impacto en los servicios ecosistémicos: una perspectiva socioeconómica

O3-15	14:45	P.Cuenca	Role of National Conservation Instruments in Improved Provisioning of Ecosystem Services in the Tropical Andean Forest
O3-16	14:55	M. Delpino Chamy	Plataforma participativa digital para la evaluación comunitaria y técnica de servicios ecosistémicos culturales.
O3-17	15:05	A.H. Hayashida Carrillo	Monitoreo de la transparencia de los recursos naturales en México.
O3-18	15:15		Questions and discussion

T2/S9a – Pathways of the biodiversity–water–food–health– climate nexus in Latin America/ Participatory approaches for sharing knowledge on ecosystem services to improve food and water securities in the face of climate change

Hosts: A.P. Turetta, A. Schuler

Room: Salón Sotaquí

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T2/S9a-1	14:00	L. Meister	Distribution of ecosystem services in southern Atlantic Rain Forest
T2/S9a-2	14:10	V.A. Roldán	Interacciones para asegurar alimento, agua, salud y contribuir a la biodiversidad en contexto de cambio climático: el caso del Valle inferior del Río Chubut
T2/S9a-3	14:20	E. Barrios	Harnessing the benefits of the biodiversity–water–food–health–climate nexus to facilitate transformative change and agroecological transitions to sustainable agrifood systems
T2/S9a-4	14:30	I. Ruiz	Local perspectives on sustainable land management
T2/S9a-5	14:40	A. De Cock	Bayesian belief networks for integrated analysis of ecosystem services related to agricultural and fisheries activities in the Guayas river basin (Ecuador)
T2/S9a-6	14:50	M. Martínez de Anguita	Evaluación de los servicios ecosistémicos de los ríos involucrando a las comunidades y escuelas rurales. Tres

		casos de estudio en Honduras, República Dominicana y Costa Rica
T2/S9a-7	15:00	Wrap up and discussion

T7b/T9b – Proyecciones y desafíos futuros de la valoración socio-económica de los servicios ecosistémicos culturales en Latinoamérica/ Food security in Wet Tropical Forests: an ecosystem services approach

Hosts: L. E. Delgado, A. Munoz, A. Tironi

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T7b-1	14:10	A. Murillas-Maza	Mejora del conocimiento de la distribución global de peces diádromos vulnerables al cambio climático y los beneficios totales obtenidos a través de los servicios ecosistémicos en los ecosistemas fluviales atlánticos de la UE
T7b-2	14:20	R. Machuca	Benefit Transfer tool: A retrieval study for the economic valuation of ecosystem services in Peru
T7b-3	14:30		Discussion with participants
T9b-1	14:45	M. Canova	Introduction and opening lecture
	14:50		Guest speaker lecture
T9b-2	14:55	A.L. De Carvalho Cruz	The paradox between Ecosystem Services availability and food security in Central Amazon: a case study based on perception
T9b-3	15:05	J. Alvarez	Conservación y restauración ecológica de ecosistemas forestales y humedales amazónicos en el Alto Huallaga, Huánuco - Perú
T9b-4	15:15		Facilitated discussion

T9a –Desafíos y visiones de los beneficios de los bosques urbanos y periurbanos en el bienestar social y salud pública

Hosts: G. Perez-Verdin, B. Kovacs, R.B. Siqueiros

Room: Salón Elqui II

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T9a-1	14:00		Welcome and session presentation by coordinators*
T9a-2	14:10	A.M. Urcuqui-Bustamante	Metodologías de trabajo colaborativo para el diseño de política pública enfocada en el manejo de bosques urbanos y periurbanos
T9a-3	14:20	M.G. Pérez-Martinez	Los servicios ecosistémicos de los árboles frondosos en ambientes urbanos: Caso de la ciudad de Durango, México.
T9a-4	14:30	A. G. Bruzó	Analysing the condition of urban ecosystems: An approach based on natural capital accounting in urban settings.
T9a-5	14:40	G.S. Binnqüist-Cervantes	Las áreas verdes y la justicia ambiental distributiva en la Ciudad de Xalapa, Ver.
T9a-6	14:50	J.M. Núñez	El mapeo del valor social del Bosque de Agua mediante el modelaje prospectivo participativo como herramienta para mejorar la gestión ambiental
T9a-7	15:00	A.M. Urcuqui-Bustamante	Non-economic values associated with payment for hydrological services programs: Recognizing local shared values to improve natural resource management
T9a-8	15:10		Conclusions of the session

Wednesday Afternoon 16:00-18:00

B10a – Climate regulation of urban environments – From models to policies

Hosts: D. La Rosa, M. Palme

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B10a-1	16:00	D. La Rosa	Introduction
B10a-2	16:05	A.G. Castaldo	Understanding Urban Ecosystem Services provided and supported by NatureBased Solutions in Latin American Cities: Insights

			and Future directions from literature review.
B10a-4	16:20	P. Muñoz Ossandón	Estrategias de intervención para el control del clima urbano: Integración de soluciones basadas en la naturaleza en el barrio histórico-patrimonial "el Almendral" de Valparaíso
B10a-5	16:40	C. Aznarez	Modelling supply-demand mismatches in ecosystem services for urban heat island mitigation and heat vulnerability
B10a-6	17:00	C. Ganem-Karlen	Microclimate assessment through the radiant heat exchange experienced by their inhabitants
B10a-7	17:20	D. La Rosa	Planning criteria of Green Infrastructure for climate regulation in hot Mediterranean climates
B10a-8	17:40	All authors	Discussion and conclusion

R2– Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro: servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica

Hosts: M. Perevochtchikova, C.I. Villegas Palacio, J.M. Galeana Pizaña

Room: Salón Sotaquí

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
R2-1	16:00	L.M. Ramírez Hernández	Servicios ecosistémicos en Colombia: normativa, políticas e instrumentos de valoración, comparación con Italia y oportunidades de desarrollo
R2-2	16:10	M. Galeana Pizaña	Dinámica de los servicios ecosistémicos en el marco de evaluaciones de impacto ambiental. El caso de los asentamientos humanos irregulares en Tlalpan, Ciudad de México
R2-3	16:20	A. Merlo Galeazzi	Impacto de los impulsores de transformación sobre los servicios ecosistémicos hidrológicos como determinante de la trayectoria irregular de una cuenca en México

R2-4	16:30	D.I Clavijo Rojas	Percepción de cambio de los Servicios Ecosistémicos en la Minería Ilícita del Oro en Latinoamérica
R2-5	16:40	P. Mokondoko	How will vulnerability and the tradeoffs between coffee yield and ecosystem services impact well-being in the future? A spatial-dynamic modelling
R2-6	16:50	L.D. Alvarado Figueroa	Evaluación de la intensificación sostenible de la ganadería bovina en los trópicos: Un caso de estudio en el sur de México
R2-7	17:00	A. Ramírez-León	El papel de las interacciones sociales en la adaptación de un sistema agroalimentario
R2-8	17:10	M. Bermudez-Urdaneta	Aproximación a la modelación de una trayectoria de largo plazo de un sistema socioecológico regional: ecología, biogeografía, arqueología y paleontología de Bogotá para reducir complejidad
R2-9	17:20	L. Diaz	The social-ecological system framework of urban wetlands: sustainable collective management

S6/T7a– Making Nature Count: Applying monetary valuation data in (financial) decision-making contexts/ Improving data on monetary values of ecosystem services: The ESVD in a global, Latin America and Caribbean context

Hosts: V. van't Hoff, M, Siebers, L. Brander

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
S6/T7a-1	16:00	V. van't Hoff/V. Guisado Goni	Introduction
S6/T7a-2	16:05	V. Guisado Goni	An ESVD deep dive: Explaining the data, the structure and the ESVD in a global, Latin America and Caribbean context
S6/T7a-3	16:25	M. Alarcon Blazquez	Ocean Accounting as an approach to track progress towards Sustainable Development
S6/T7a-4	16:35	V. Guisado Goni	Discussion and Questions

S6/T7a-5	16:50	V. van't Hoff	Making Nature Count – Insights about the integration of ecosystem services valuation data in financial decision-making
S6/T7a-6	17:10	C. Ramírez Cabrera	Changes in the Economic Value of Ecosystem Services due to Land Cover and Land Use Dynamics in Oaxaca, Mexico
S6/T7a-7	17:20	T. Tadesse	Cost-Benefit Analysis of Sustainable Land Management Interventions: Evidence from Southern Ethiopia
S6/T7a-8	17:30	Luiz Magelhaes Filho	Assessing the impacts of climate and socio-economic scenarios on ecosystem service values in the Atlantic coastal zone.
S6/T7a-9	17:40	V. van't Hoff	Discussion and conclusions

T18c- Quantification and Valuation of ecosystem services: pathway to connect research and public policies in Latin America

Hosts: A. Paula Turetta, I. Lopes Batista, M. van Weelden

Room: Salón Incahuasi

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation	
T18c-1	16:00	I. Lopes	Overview about quantification and valuation of ecosystem services in Latin America
T18c-2	16:20	P.J. Bergamo	Pollination ecology: understanding the dynamics of use and provision of ecosystem services in agricultural environments
T18c-3	16:50	E. Noellemeyer	Monitoring and certification of carbon sequestration and sustainable soil management
T18c-4	17:20	M. van Weelden	Capitals Coalition initiative
T18c-5	17:40		Discussion and wrap up

T20 – Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America

Hosts: F. Benra, L. Nahuelhual

Room: Salón Elqui II

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
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T20-1	16:00	K. Huaiquimilla Guerrero	Desposesión y Gobernanza: El rol invisible de los pueblos indígenas en las áreas naturales protegidas de Chile
T20-2	16:15	L. Nahuelhual	The ecosystem service concept as a lens to analyze distributive inequalities
T20-3	16:30		World café session with all authors

● Day 3: Thursday, 9 November 2023

Thursday Morning 11:00–12:30

B8 – Operativización de los servicios ecosistémicos para la gestión de los ecosistemas de montaña

Hosts: C.C. Caro Vera, V.M.J. Soares Mantas, P. Marquet

Room: Salón Elqui II

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B8-1	11:00 C. Caro	Agrupación de servicios ecosistémicos para facilitar su operacionalización en la gestión de ecosistemas altoandinos del Perú
B8-2	11:10 V. Mantas	Mapping Global Ecosystem Services through Cloud Computing and Local Knowledge Integration
B8-3	11:20 R. Campos García	Capacidad de almacenamiento de carbono en humedales andinos ubicados al sur de la Reserva Nacional de Junín, año 2022.
B8-4	11:30 K. Eckhardt	Effect of Ecological Restoration on carbon supply for a montane forest in the central Andes of Peru.
B8-5	11:40 J. Diaz	El impacto del fuego en la oferta de servicios ecosistémicos de los Páramos
B8-6	11:50 H. Zaman	Valuing the Cryosphere: Defining the principles and classification for glacier related accounts and ecosystem services

B8-7	12:00	J.P. Araya	Conocimiento de la diversidad microbiana como aporte para la conservación de ecosistemas de alta montaña.
B8-8	12:10	A. Sperotto	Incorporating Ecosystem Services into the Water-Energy-Food Nexus: Opportunities for a transformative change in Mountain Regions
B8-9	12:20	A. Marquez Torres	Integración del mapeo del riesgo de incendios para una gestión efectiva de los ecosistemas vulnerables: Cordillera del Pirineo, Europa

B10d – Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities

Hosts: T. Gadda

Room: Salón Incahuasi

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B10d-1	11:10	E.A.A Larbi	Thriving in a polluted system; macroinvertebrates as indicators of the quality of the Densu river in Ghana.
B10d-2	11:30	N.N. Badger	Bacteria Water Quality of the Densu River in the Ga Municipality of Accra, Weija – Ghana
B10d-4	11:50	R.A. Kolcsár	Linking ecosystem condition to services in urban microclimate regulation – a critical interpretive synthesis

T18a – Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design: Coproducing in the interface of science and practice

Hosts: P. Ruggiero, N. Nascimento

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T18a-1	11:00	P. Ruggiero	Introduction
T18a-2	11:10	G.A. Perila	The more we share, the more we know: Collaborative modelling of nature contributions with local citizenry aiming to design public policies

T18a-3	11:30	S. Bratanova-Doncheva	Stakeholder involvement process in the ecosystem services assessment and management as part of Long-Term Socio-Ecological Research
T18a-4	11:50	J. Assis	A serious game to share knowledge about landscape tradeoffs between agriculture and ecosystem services and to inform planning
T18a-5	12:10	J. Spangenberg	The European Green belt: a multi-purpose refugium

S9c – Towards developing effective PES mechanisms suiting Indigenous peoples and local communities

Hosts: K.K. Sangha, M. Hernandez

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
S9c-1	11:00	K.K. Sangha	Introduction to the session: Need to develop IPLCs-specific PES systems
S9c-2	11:05	J.P. Whitt	Operacionalizar los "Principios de integridad para la distribución de beneficios en las SbN forestales para la mitigación del cambio climático" de WWF
S9c-3	11:20	Y. Lin	Achieving sustainable land management in indigenous community with the methods of ecosystem services assessment
S9c-4	11:35	P.H. Mallick	Assessing Village-level dependence on Provisioning Ecosystem Services from Tropical Deciduous Forest in Midnapore, West Bengal, India to guide management decisions
S9c-5	11:50	B.K. Ireri	Prospects of Willingness to Pay in Restoration of Water Quality and Water Quantity Ecosystem Services in Kapingazi Catchment, Embu County, Kenya
S9c-6	12:05	D. Tovar	Pago por Servicios Ambientales en Páramos de Colombia: Lecciones aprendidas
S9c-7	12:20		Discussion and conclusion

T18e– Servicios ecosistémicos en la toma de decisiones: ¿su aplicación ha promovido cambios en la política ambiental chilena?

Hosts: A.J. Allendes, D.R. Vasquez, F.D. Galdames, L. Nahuelhual

Room: Salón Sotaquí

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T18e-1	11:00 D. Rozas	Analysis of the Integration of Ecosystem Services at Multiple Levels of Decision-Making: Evolution of the Regulatory Framework and Practical Applications in Land-use Planning
T18e-2	11:15 B. Bularz	Are Chilean TURFs a management strategy adequate to ensure the sustainability of the ecosystem services present in coastal areas? Evidence based on a historical performance assessment at a national level
T18e-3	11:30 A. Jaramillo	"Incorporating Ecosystem Services Approach into Chile's Environmental Policy: How Far Have We Progressed?"
T18e-4	11:45 L. Nahuelhual	Why do some concepts generate lasting changes in environmental policy and others don't? The example of ecosystem services
T18e-5	12:00	Discussion

Thursday Afternoon 14:00–15:30

B10d – Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities

Hosts: T. Gadda

Room: Salón Incahuasi

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
B10d-1	14:10 K.V. Salako,	Local perception of mangrove provisioning ecosystem services, and disservices and willingness to pay for their conservation: a case study in Benin, West-Africa

B10d-2	14:30	P. R. Ranasnghe	Ecosystem Services in Cities: Assessing New York City Bluebelt System with the UN Ecosystem Restoration Decade Mandate
B10d-3	14:50	G. Pradilla	Blue Infrastructure as a Multifunctional Space: Comparative Analysis of Ecosystem Services in Colombian City Master Plans
B10d-4	15:10	T. Negrin Marques	Identificación de servicios ecosistémicos urbanos utilizando la técnica del photovoice en estudiantes universitarios

O1 – Young Ecosystem Services Specialists Network (YESS-ESP): Experiencias desde Latinoamérica y el Caribe

Hosts: A.R. Franco, N. Weins, A. Bernal-Escobar, G. Avila-Flores, B. Izidio

Room: Salón Sotaquí II

Time	Name	Title of the Presentation	
O1-1	14:00	A.R. Franco	YESS: Quiénes somos y qué hacemos por Latinoamérica y el Caribe
O1-2	14:15	C. Eliff	Perspectives from the Young Researcher Program of the Brazilian Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
O1 - 3	14:30	S. Roldan	Evaluación del capital natural y su efecto sobre los servicios ecosistémicos de aprovisionamiento hidrológico en la zona alta de la Cuenca del Río Coca caso de estudio: Parque Nacional Cayambe Coca
O1-4	14:45	F.H.C. Lima	Ecosystem Services and Traditional Agriculture of the Tremembé Ethnicity banks of the of the river Mundaú – Ceará- Brazil

B1b – Mangle defender: Un juego para enfrentar las mudanzas climáticas con ayuda de los servicios ecosistémicos

Hosts: P. A. Casas Cortes, L. J. Castañeda

Room: Salón Sotaquí

O2/T15 – Ecosystem services and human well-being in Latin America: a relationship or an assumption?/ Social vulnerabilities and Ecosystem Services: an emerging issue

Hosts: V.H. Marin, L.E. Delgado

Room: Salón Elqui I

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
O2/T15-1	14:00	M. Sánchez-Mejía	Biodiversidad para todos. Valoración y remuneración de la biodiversidad y los servicios ecosistémicos y su relación con el bienestar, en los territorios en Colombia.
O2/T15-2	14:15	F. Benra	Mismatches in the ecosystem services-wellbeing nexus: a case study for Chilean Patagonia
O2/T15-3	14:30	M. Barceló	Perceptions of land-sea interactions and ecosystem services and its contribution to human well-being in the Valdivian coast, Southern Chile.
O2/T15-4	14:45	S. Uribe	Turismo, servicios ecosistémicos culturales y vulnerabilidad social
O2/T15-5	15:00	R. Castro-Díaz	Towards a Social Vulnerability and Ecosystem Services Index (SVESI) for exploring local communities' nature dependence

S1b – Agri-environmental indicators of Brazil: Strategic intelligence for agricultural sustainability, based on the maintenance of Ecosystem Services

Hosts: M. Simoes, R. Ferraz, P. Freitas, B. Alves

Room: Salón Elqui II

T18a – Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design: Coproducing in the interface of science and practice

Hosts: P. Ruggiero, N. Nascimento

Room: Salón Elqui III

	Time	Name	Title of the Presentation
T18a-1	14:00	F. Costa	Adherence Of The Brazilian Environmental Zoning Regulations To The Concept Of Ecosystem Services
T18a-2	14:20	N.N. Nascimento	Coproduction in climate policy formulation: navigating challenges and achieving impact in São Paulo state – Brazil
T18a-3	14:40	P. Ruggiero	Identifying ways of thinking about coproduction between scientists and decision makers using Q methodology
T18a-4	15:10		Conclusion

Appendix II.

Detailed posters program

This poster session will be held on **Wednesday 8th November** from **14:00 to 15:30**. The list below shows the sessions that will be in the program. We invite all to join the poster sessions.

Biome Working Group Posters (B)

B8 – Operativización de los servicios ecosistémicos para la gestión de los ecosistemas de montaña

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
B8-1	J. Araya Angel	Conocimiento de la diversidad microbiana como aporte para la conservación de ecosistemas de alta montaña.
B8-2	C.J. Galarza	Verification of Forest Ecosystem Services at FSC

Regional Chapter Group Posters (R)

R2 – Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro: servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
R2-1	S. Torres Mallma	Áreas Naturales Protegidas en la Ciudad, Humedales Urbanos de Lima. Mapeando Los Pantanos de Villa: recuperando sus fronteras de vida silvestre.

Sectoral Working Group Posters (S)

S6 – Making Nature Count: Applying monetary valuation data in (financial) decision-making contexts

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
S6-1	A. Gomes da Silva	The economic valuation of ecosystem services provided by protected areas: a systematic review

S7 – Tourism as an ecosystem service – Challenges and opportunities for research and practice / El turismo como servicio ecosistémico – Retos y oportunidades para investigación y practica

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
S7-1	G.Rebolledo	Valoración social y ecológica de la biodiversidad de aves y manifers marinos en dos localidades de la zona costera Norte de Chile.
S7-2	C. Pellicer	Fortaleciendo el turismo desde el desarrollo de la identidad basada en la naturaleza y el valor ecológico del territorio, para

promover la sostenibilidad y la importancia de los servicios ambientales.

S9b – Experiencias de monitoreo comunitario participativo de biodiversidad y servicios ecosistémicos en Latinoamérica y el Caribe

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
S9b-1	C. Sazo	Zona Norte de Quilpué, un refugio de bienestar en la ciudad.

Thematic Working Group Posters (T)

T1 – Evaluación participativa de servicios ecosistémicos: Herramientas para desarrollar un ejercicio transdisciplinario en el contexto latinoamericano / Participatory assessment of ecosystem services: Tools for a transdisciplinary exercise in Latin America.

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T1-1	I. Eyzaguirre	Observatorio del Manglar y sus Matorros: ciencia y datos abiertos para efectivizar la gobernanza ambiental de los servicios ecosistémicos

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T1-2	M. Aldave	La voz de los niños en la conservación del humedal urbano y Sitio Ramsar Pantanos de Villa en Lima Metropolitana, Perú.

T4c – Mapeo, análisis y modelamiento de beneficios de la naturaleza (servicios ecosistémicos y contribuciones de la naturaleza) a nivel local: vínculos urbano-rurales

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T4c-1	A.Cueto	Análisis socioecológico de los humedales en la Isla Grande de Chiloé: turberas y pomponales como casos de estudio

T5 – Servicios ecosistémicos FAIR para la reducción de riesgos y como eje para la gestión sostenible del terreno / FAIR ecosystem services accounting for risk reduction and ES as a basis for sustainable land management

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T5-1	A.Rondon	Bridging the gap between ecosystem services conservation and rural landscape development in post-conflict regions: A case study from San José del Guaviare, Colombia

T6a – Valoración plura de la biodiversidad

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T6a-1	G. Simões	Evaluation of habitat quality and valuation of biodiversity aspects in the APA de São Francisco Xavier (APA-SFX): an integrated approach based on landscape analysis

T7b – Proyecciones y desafíos futuros de la valoración socio-económica de los servicios ecosistémicos culturales en Latinoamérica

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T7b-1	A.Camelo	Analysis of the Influence of Distance to Protected Areas in the Federal District, Brazil

T8 – Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services

ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
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T8-1	M.Sylla	Assessment of the potential of selected landscapes of Poland to provide landscape services
T8-2	M. Valladares Antón	Disaster memory and regulating services in El Culebron wetland (Coquimbo, Chile).
T15- Social vulnerabilities and Ecosystem Services: an emerging issue		
ID	Name	Title of the Presentation
T15-1	A.C. Copier Guerra	Sobre la falta de manejo integrado de la cuenca del río Maipo: resultados de un modelo DPSIR

Appendix III.

Timetable and Rooms Overview

Tuesday, 7th November 2023		Room
11:00-12:30	T8-Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	T4b-Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action	Salón Elqui II
	R1-El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios	Salón Sotaquí
	T4c-Mapeo, análisis y modelamiento de beneficios de la naturaleza (servicios ecosistémicos y contribuciones de la naturaleza) a nivel local vínculos urbano-rurales	Salón Incahuasi
	S8a - ¿Cómo incorporar los servicios ecosistémicos en la planificación de la conservación	Salón Elqui I
	B2-A review of the current state of the ecosystem services of wetlands in the Amazon region	Online room 1
	O3-Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice	Online room 2
14:00-15:30	T8-Understanding Cultural Ecosystem Services	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	T4b-Using Ecosystem Services to prioritise conservation action	Salón Elqui II
	R1-El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios + S9b-Experiencias de monitoreo comunitario participativo de biodiversidad y servicios	Salón Sotaquí
	B1a-Compartiendo experiencias en la evaluación y valoración de los servicios ecosistémicos de los manglares en América Latina y el Caribe	Salón Incahuasi
	T16 - From Science to Practice A pragmatic guide to verifying and financing positive impacts on ecosystem services	Salón Elqui I
	T6b - Valuación económica de la pérdida de servicios ambientales de ecosistemas costeros bajo un contexto de incremento del nivel del mar	Online room 1
	T18d-Towards a certification and labelling scheme based on the ecosystem services approach	Online room 2

16:00-18:00	T1-Participatory assessment of ecosystem services Tools for a transdisciplinary exercise in Latin America	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	S7-Tourism as an ecosystem service - Challenges and opportunities for research and practice El turismo como servicio ecosistémico Retos y oportunidades para investigación y practica	Salón Elqui II
	R1-El enfoque socioecológico para el monitoreo comunitario participativo de servicios	Salón Sotaquí
	B3a - El verdadero valor del bosque Diálogos y reflexión desde la perspectiva sudamericana	Salón Incahuasi
	S3a-Fast-growing Forest plantations what kind of services and disservices + B3b-Ecosystem services of forests in the face of climate change	Salón Elqui I
	S8b-Soil ecosystem services (SES) bringing out of invisibility and supporting decision-making	Online room 1

Wednesday, 8th November 2023		Room
11:00-12:30	S3b - Climate, Biodiversity and Restoration How to articulate them in the Forest Policy	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	T20-Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America	Salón Elqui II
	R2-Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica	Salón Sotaquí
	T5-FAIR ecosystem services accounting for risk reduction and ES as a basis for sustainable land management + T6a-FAIR ecosystem services accounting for risk reduction and ES as a basis for sustainable land management	Salón Incahuasi
	T14-Integrating Nature-based solutions in spatial planning for tackling climate change and	Salón Elqui I
14:00-15:30	B10b-Research on urban ecosystem services. The state of the art and challenges for future	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	T9a-Desafíos y visiones de los beneficios de los bosques urbanos y periurbanos en el bienestar	Salón Elqui II
	T2- Pathways of the biodiversity-water-food-health-climate nexus in Latin America + S9a- Participatory approaches for sharing knowledge on ecosystem services to improve	Salón Sotaquí

	O3–Emerging issues in ES science, policy & practice	Salón Incahuasi
	T7b– Proyecciones y desafíos futuros de la valoración socio-económica de los servicios + T9b–Food security in Wet Tropical Forests an ecosystem services approach	Salón Elqui I
16:00–18:00	S6–Making Nature Count Applying monetary valuation data in (financial) decision-making contexts + T7a–Improving data on monetary values of ecosystem services The ESVD in a global, Latin America and Caribbean context	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	T20–Equity and justice perspectives from Latin America	Salón Elqui II
	R2–Viendo el pasado para proyectar el futuro servicios ecosistémicos en y desde el enfoque de trayectorias socioecológicas en Latinoamérica	Salón Sotaquí
	T18c–Quantification and Valuation of ecosystem services pathway to connect research and public policies in Latin America	Salón Incahuasi
	B10a–Climate regulation of urban environments – From models to policies	Salón Elqui I

Thursday, 9th November 2023		Room
11:00–12:30	T18a–Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design Coproducing in the interface of science and practice	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	B8–Operativización de los servicios ecosistémicos para la gestión de los ecosistemas de montaña	Salón Elqui II
	T18e–Servicios ecosistémicos en la toma de decisiones su aplicación ha promovido cambios en la política ambiental chilena	Salón Sotaquí
	B10d–Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities	Salón Incahuasi
	S9c–Towards developing effective PES mechanisms suiting Indigenous peoples and local	Salón Elqui I
14:00–15:30	T18a–Bridging Ecosystem Services and Policy Design Coproducing in the interface of science and practice	Salón Elqui III (Plenary Room)
	O1–Young Ecosystem Services Specialists Network (YESS–ESP) Experiencias desde Latinoamérica y el Caribe.	Salón Elqui II
	B1b – Mangle defender Un juego para enfrentar las mudanzas climáticas con ayuda de los servicios ecosistémicos	Salón Sotaquí
	B10d–Ecosystem Services in and Beyond Cities	Salón Incahuasi

	O2-Ecosystem services and human well-being in Latin America a relationship or an assumption + T15-Social vulnerabilities and Ecosystem Services an emerging issue	Salón Elqui I
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Appendix IV.

Conference Program Overview

Date/ Time	Monday November 06	Tuesday November 07	Wednesday November 08	Thursday November 09	Friday November 10
8:30	Pre-conference workshop & trainings	Registration	Registration	Registration	Field trips
9:00		Opening Keynote(s) Talk & discussion	Opening Keynote(s) Talk & discussion	Opening Keynote(s) Talk & discussion	
10:30		Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	
11:00		Paralell sessions: B2, S8a, S9a, T4b, T4c, T8, R1, O3 (1,5 hr)	Paralell sessions: S3b, T5, T6a, T14, T20, R2 (1,5 hr)	Paralell sessions: B8, B10d, S9c, T18a, T18e (1,5 hr)	
12:30		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	
14:00		Paralell sessions: B1a, S9b, T4b, T6b, T8, T16, T18d, R1 (1,5 hr)	Paralell sessions: B10b, T2, T7b, T9a, T9b, S9a, O3 (1,5 hr)	Paralell sessions: B1b, B10d, S1b, T15, T18a, O1, O2 (1,5 hr)	
15:30	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break		
16:00	Registration	Paralell sessions: B3a, B3b, B5, S3a, S7, S8b, T1, R1 (2 hrs)	Paralell sessions: B10a, S6, T7a, T18c, T20, R2 (2 hrs)	Reflection on the conference & panel discussion	
17:00	Opening Ceremony			Awards & Closing ceremony	
18:00	Welcome reception & Entertainment	Astronomy experience (18:00 – 24:00)	Poster session & Market Place		
19:00			Conference dinner		

*Sharing knowledge about ecosystem services
and natural capital to build a sustainable future*

4th ESP LAC 2023
International conference
La Serena, Chile, 6–10 November